

Dabigatran etexilate and COVID-19

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ABSTRACT

Thrombotic complications are frequent in COVID-19. There is evidence supporting the use of prophylactic dose low molecular weight heparin (LMWH) as prophylaxis for venous thromboembolism in critically ill patients. Indeed, all patients with COVID-19 that are admitted to hospital should receive prophylactic dose of LMWH. Dabigatran etexilate (Pradaxa) is an active direct thrombin inhibitor that inhibits clot-bound and circulating thrombin. Based on virtual screening results dabigatran etexilate is also a potential SARS-CoV-2 inhibitor. Therefore, dabigatran could be a new therapeutic option for the prophylaxis and treatment of COVID-19 associated thromboembolism, but further clinical research is mandatory.

INTRODUCTION

Thrombotic complications are frequent in COVID-19 and contribute significantly to mortality and morbidity. Mechanisms of hypercoagulability that may be upregulated in COVID-19 are immune-mediated thrombotic mechanisms, complement activation, macrophage activation syndrome, antiphospholipid antibody syndrome, hyperferritinemia, and renin-angiotensin system dysregulation¹.

There is evidence supporting the use of prophylactic dose low molecular weight heparin (LMWH) as prophylaxis for venous thromboembolism in critically ill patients. In view of the hypercoagulable state of patients with severe COVID-19, and the potential increased risk of thrombosis, all patients with COVID-19 that are admitted to hospital should receive this prophylactic treatment in the absence of medical contraindications. If LMWH is not available, unfractionated heparin could be used, although this requires more frequent injections; an alternative is fondaparinux, but whether this drug has the postulated anti-inflammatory benefits of heparin is unclear. Patients with severe COVID-19 might need higher-dose thromboprophylaxis than is generally given because of their hypercoagulable state, and this hypothesis will be tested in several multicentre, randomised, controlled trials².

DABIGATRAN

Dabigatran etexilate (Pradaxa) is an orally administered prodrug that is converted in the liver to dabigatran, an active direct thrombin inhibitor that inhibits clot-bound and circulating thrombin. It is used in the prevention and management of venous thromboembolic (VTE) disease, in stroke

prevention in patients with atrial fibrillation (AF), and in ischemic heart disease. Dabigatran should not be used in patients with prosthetic heart valves or during pregnancy.

Dosing in VTE primary prophylaxis in surgical patients is 110 mg one to four hours after surgery, followed by 220 mg once daily for 28 to 35 days (hip replacement) or 10 days (knee replacement). Dosing for treatment and secondary prevention of VTE is 150 mg orally twice daily after 5 to 10 days of parenteral anticoagulation if creatinine clearance is >30 mL/minute. Dosing for stroke prevention in AF is 110 mg orally twice daily or 150 mg orally twice daily if CrCl >30 mL/minute. European labelling suggests dose reduction in patients older than 75 years (150 mg once per day or 110 mg orally twice per day). Product labeling in the United States recommends avoidance of dabigatran in individuals with CrCl <15 mL/minute or in those who are hemodialysis dependent; the Canadian, United Kingdom, and European Medicines Agency labeling recommend avoidance in patients with a CrCl <30 mL/minute³.

Virtual screening results of RdRp demonstrated that dabigatran etexilat might be potential SARS-CoV-2 inhibitor. Based on structure modeling of helicase protein dabigatran is predicted to be helicase inhibitor with high mfScores through virtual ligand screening. On the basis of virtual

screening results of small-molecule compounds against Spike protein dabigatran showed high binding affinity⁴.

THESIS

As dabigatran is both anticoagulant and potential SARS-CoV-2 inhibitor based on virtual screening results, it could be a new therapeutic option for the prophylaxis and treatment of COVID-19 associated thromboembolism, but further clinical research is mandatory.

REFERENCES

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